

Leveraging FAIR-compliant standards for data management and provenance towards building an interpretable genomic translator for human cellular architecture maps in the Bridge2AI program

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ABSTRACT

In this short paper, we discuss the FAIRness and AI-readiness tools we built for the development of the Cell Maps for Artificial Intelligence (CM4AI) initial data release, an NIH-sponsored component of its Bridge2AI program intended to lay a basis for broad adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods in biomedicine. Tools discussed here include packages to validate, generate, and parse FAIR-compliant RO-Crate packages with schema.org and other standard vocabulary metadata, including deep resolvable provenance graphs of datasets, software, and computations, using the Evidence Graph Ontology (EVI).

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Computing methodologies** → **Knowledge representation and reasoning**; **Machine learning**.

KEYWORDS

FAIR, Bridge2AI, provenance, cell map, genomic, CM4AI

1 INTRODUCTION

Cell Maps for Artificial Intelligence (CM4AI) is one of four "Data Generation Projects" in the flagship NIH Bridge2AI program. The goal of these projects is to advance biomedical research by laying the basis for the broad adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods for complex biomedical research problems. [11]

CM4AI will produce interpretable cellular architecture maps showing protein interaction, association, and location at multiple resolutions for distinct human cell lines and intervention conditions (e.g. treated and untreated breast cancer cell lines). Unlike current hierarchical models of cell structure and protein-protein interactions

(PPI), these maps will be cell-line- and perturbation-specific. The models are envisioned to be substrates for the development of AI Deep Learning (AI/DL) algorithms that are directly interpretable by cell biologists as to what cellular components (elements of protein machinery) are affected by specific perturbations. This is a critical determination in genotype-phenotype studies in therapeutic drug development.

The computational steps in CM4AI are based on preliminary work in multiple laboratories [9, 13, 14, 17] and are currently being extended with additional data modalities and made reproducibly robust with output designed to support AI-readiness and reuse in the CM4AI Data Generation Project. The CM4AI Tools pipeline steps used in producing the cell architecture maps employ AI/ML models at several stages where decisions are made that are not transparent to the users. By capturing FAIR-compliant metadata and complete provenance based on the standards for data management, comprised of the computational steps and underlying resources in the models, these complex data transitions can become more interpretable to the user with improved explainability and FAIRness[16]. Provenance graphs constructed for these maps provide a basis for further pre-model AI explainability (XAI) work and ultimately for both pre-model and post-model XAI [1].

2 METHODS AND TOOLS

CM4AI cell maps are constructed in a complex reusable "Tools" pipeline which takes data from multiple experimental modalities, generates and merges embeddings of the cell interactions proximities and locations, and builds the map. Embeddings for affinity purification mass spectroscopy (AP-MS) datasets are computed using a node2vec [3] generated model. These are merged with protein localization image data computed using a densenet [5] model, by a further AI approach. In the preliminary work this was done using

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a random forest model, in the current work an unsupervised model is used.

The Tools pipeline calls our FAIRSCAPE-CLI (CLI) product at each significant computational step. FAIRSCAPE-CLI is a Python package installable from PyPI, and callable from the command-line interface, that is used to annotate resources with schema.org [4] and other standard metadata terms, and validate that metadata against data dictionaries before packaging them in RO-Crate [2, 15] format, a popular FAIR (meta)data packaging standard.

The CLI uses the Pydantic [12] data validation library for creating metadata models based on the names, definitions, and attributes outlined in the data dictionaries. When metadata about the resources are submitted by the users for annotation, instances of dataset, software, and computation models are created once they are successfully validated against their respective models. These instances are then added to the RO-Crate metadata terms set. During this process, the CLI fetches all datasets and software objects from the locations specified in the metadata, downloads these objects, and populates the RO-Crate with them. The RO-Crate package produced by the CLI contains both objects and their metadata describing them, making it an ideal candidate for transporting data and metadata.

We have implemented additional features to load RO-Crates and reuse their components in meaningful ways in FAIRSCAPE 2.0, a digital commons environment based on the original FAIRSCAPE [8] framework, with significant revisions to simplify deployment and maintenance, and to enable remote instantiation of evidence (provenance) graphs. FAIRSCAPE 2.0 runs in a Kubernetes environment at the University of Virginia and provides APIs for loading RO-Crates into the commons environment, validating the upload contents, registering the annotated datasets, software, and computations with persistent identifiers, and creating deep FAIR-compliant provenance graphs based on a formal ontology, EVI – the Evidence Graph Ontology [1, 10]. It can readily be deployed in public clouds.

While in the original FAIRSCAPE framework, all computations were run directly in the commons environment, introducing the CLI package allows for computations to be run remotely on disparate computing resources not directly connected to the FAIRSCAPE commons, while still maintaining metadata consistency and correctness. The FAIRSCAPE CLI is also capable of repackaging RO-Crates in BagIt format [7] for upload into Dataverse [6] instances. Dataverse is an NIH-approved general-purpose data repository with over 100 installations worldwide.

Figure 1 shows the interoperation of multiple data modality pipelines with FAIRSCAPE-CLI and the FAIRSCAPE digital commons.

An alpha data release of CM4AI preliminary data is up as of September 2023 on the CM4AI.org website.

3 RESULTS

The FAIRSCAPE-CLI tools were tested on all computational steps as part of a pipeline to create a unified hierarchical map of human cell architecture from protein fluorescent images and protein biophysical association data. For every step, FAIRSCAPE-CLI was used to annotate all datasets, software, and computations with descriptive metadata before packaging them as an RO-Crate. These RO-Crates

Figure 1: CM4AI FAIR data, software, and computation integration with FAIRSCAPE-CLI and the FAIRSCAPE commons.

were then loaded onto FAIRSCAPE 2.0, disassembled, and validated against the metadata before being registered with persistent identifiers. Complete provenance graphs were then generated outlining the connections among the inputs and outputs to the computations, all of which are searchable and resolvable.

Future work planned for 2023-2024 includes implementing dataset-specific schema validation and formatting – essentially mini-data dictionaries for each dataset; resolution of queries to loaded RO-Crates in FAIRSCAPE 2.0 to the individual datasets and software package contents; and support for registration and validation of large-scale CRISPR-perturbation single-cell RNA-seq datasets and embeddings in the revised Tools pipeline.

4 CONCLUSION

The introduction of FAIRSCAPE and Evidence Graph Ontology (EVI) tools allows users to package research results with metadata, to disclose how these results were derived through FAIR-compliant evidence graphs as provenance, and to understand the complete pipeline that generates the unified hierarchical map of human cell architecture.

5 RESOURCE AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The FAIRSCAPE-CLI software package is here: <https://github.com/fairscape/fairscape-cli> and the initial CM4AI alpha data release is here: <https://discovery.informatics.uab.edu/apex/r/tkg/cm4ai/data>.

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